

Endurance Study: A retrospective non-interventional study to evaluate seizure liability using human cortical organoid technology

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1. Introduction

Seizure liability remains an important safety consideration identified during both clinical development and post-marketing use of small molecule drugs. Neurological adverse events, including both seizures occurring at therapeutic exposure levels and withdrawal-associated seizure phenomena, are often detected after initial human exposure, where they may influence dose selection, labeling, and risk mitigation strategies.

The present study is designed as a retrospective evaluation of drugs with previously characterized clinical outcomes, using a human iPSC-derived cortical organoid model that captures emergent neuronal network behavior and synaptic function [1]. Prior work has demonstrated that functional endpoints derived from this model may detect perturbations in neuronal activity at concentrations below those associated with overt cytotoxicity [2], supporting its utility in early hazard identification.

This protocol describes the planned evaluation of drug-induced changes in network-level activity following controlled exposure across pharmacokinetically anchored concentration ranges. The study is intended to assess whether assay-derived functional signatures are associated with known clinical seizure risk and to support future applications in prospective safety assessment [3].

2. Study Design Overview

This study is a retrospective, non-interventional evaluation of a predefined set of small molecule drugs with known clinical seizure risk profiles. Drugs will be assessed in a human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived cortical organoid model following acute exposure across a concentration range scaled to observed human pharmacokinetics. Study procedures, cohort definitions, and analytical approaches are specified in advance to guide consistent evaluation across drugs and to support drug-level comparisons.

3. Drug Selection

3.1 Eligibility Criteria

Drugs were selected for inclusion based on the availability of either well-documented human clinical outcomes related to seizure liability, totaling a patient population of 120,551, or known positive controls (Table 1). Eligible drugs were restricted to small molecule entities with defined chemical structure and established pharmacokinetic characterization. The study set

includes drugs spanning a range of clinical seizure risk profiles, including (1) drugs associated with seizure events occurring within the therapeutic exposure range and (2) drugs associated with seizure activity observed in the context of withdrawal or discontinuation. A comparator set of drugs known to be CNS-penetrant, but without documented seizure liability was also identified to support classification performance. Cohort assignment was based on curated human data sources, including regulatory filings, clinical trial reports, and published literature.

Drugs will be obtained from established commercial vendors with demonstrated quality standards, including but not limited to Cayman Chemical, MedChemExpress, SelleckChem, and Sigma–Aldrich. Materials will be required to meet vendor-provided analytical specifications, typically including $\geq 95\%$ purity as determined by HPLC or LC-MS, with supporting certificates of analysis confirming identity and stability. Where multiple sources are available, preference will be given to drugs with consistent analytical characterization across suppliers. Finally, each drug must have an unambiguous structural definition represented by a canonical SMILES string to enable downstream cheminformatics analysis.

Table 1 – Drugs selected for inclusion in endurance study.

Drug Name	Neurotoxicity Classification	Reference(s)
5-Aminovaleric acid	No Neurotoxicity	[6]
Acetaminophen	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Ambroxol	No Neurotoxicity	[7–8]
Aspirin	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Beclamide	No Neurotoxicity	[9–10]
Bicifadine	No Neurotoxicity	[11]
BMS 204352	No Neurotoxicity	[12–13]
Caffeine	No Neurotoxicity	[14]
Cyclizine	No Neurotoxicity	[15–16]
Cyclothiazide	No Neurotoxicity	[17–18]
Diclofenac	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Diethylstilbestrol	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Dopamine	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Droxidopa	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Fipronil	No Neurotoxicity	[19]
Gabazine	No Neurotoxicity	[20–21]
Ibuprofen	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Iprindole	No Neurotoxicity	[22]
Lamotrigine	No Neurotoxicity	[23–26]
Lazabemide	No Neurotoxicity	[27–31]
LY 450108	No Neurotoxicity	[32–33]
Mepazine	No Neurotoxicity	[34–35]
Naproxen	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Nicotine	No Neurotoxicity	[36]
Nifedipine	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
Norepinephrine	No Neurotoxicity	[7]
NS 1643	No Neurotoxicity	[37–39]
Ondansetron	No Neurotoxicity	[40]
Orphenadrine	No Neurotoxicity	[41–42]

Table 1 (continued)

Drug Name	Neurotoxicity Classification	Reference(s)
Ralfinamide	No Neurotoxicity	[43]
Rimegepant	No Neurotoxicity	[44]
Rislenemdaz	No Neurotoxicity	[45]
Sotuletinib	No Neurotoxicity	[46-47]
Tianeptine	No Neurotoxicity	[48]
Tropisetron	No Neurotoxicity	[49-50]
Xanomeline	No Neurotoxicity	[51]
Amfepramone	Seizure Risk	[52]
Aminophylline	Seizure Risk	[7, 53]
Aminopyridine	Seizure Risk	[7, 54]
Bay K 8644	Seizure Risk	[55]
Bicuculline	Seizure Risk	[56-57]
Bicuculline methiodide	Seizure Risk	[56-57]
Bromocriptine	Seizure Risk	[23]
Bupropion	Seizure Risk	[23]
Carbamazepine	Seizure Risk	[7]
Clozapine	Seizure Risk	[23]
Ethosuximide	Seizure Risk	[7]
Famotidine	Seizure Risk	[7, 58-60]
Flumazenil	Seizure Risk	[7, 61-62]
Hydrastine	Seizure Risk	[7, 63-64]
Indomethacin	Seizure Risk	[7, 65]
Kainic Acid	Seizure Risk	[66-68]
Lindane	Seizure Risk	[69-70]
Maprotiline	Seizure Risk	[70]
Meperidine	Seizure Risk	[71-72]
Metrizamide	Seizure Risk	[73-74]
Mexiletine	Seizure Risk	[7, 70]
Minaprine	Seizure Risk	[75]
NMDA	Seizure Risk	[76-78]
Penicillin	Seizure Risk	[7, 79-80]
Quetiapine	Seizure Risk	[23]
Ropivacaine	Seizure Risk	[23, 81-83]
Rufinamide	Seizure Risk	[7, 84-86]
Strychnine	Seizure Risk	[6, 87]
Tiagabine	Seizure Risk	[7, 88]
Venlafaxine	Seizure Risk	[23, 89]

3.2 Exclusion Criteria

Drugs were excluded where clinical safety data are insufficient or ambiguous with respect to seizure outcomes, where pharmacokinetic parameters required for exposure scaling were unavailable, or where physicochemical properties (toxic solvent, solubility limits) preclude testing within an interpretable concentration range. Non-small molecule modalities were not considered within the scope of this study.

3.3 Exposure Strategy

Test concentrations will be selected relative to reported human exposure levels, using maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) and, where available, fraction unbound to inform pharmacologically relevant ranges. Drugs will be evaluated across a multi-point concentration series spanning approximately two orders of magnitude below and above C_{max} with adjustments made as needed to account for solubility, binding, or assay constraints.

4. Readouts and Data Acquisition

4.1 Calcium Imaging Assay

Functional activity will be assessed using fluorescence-based calcium imaging performed on a FLIPR Tetra system (Molecular Devices). Organoids will be loaded with Calcium 6 reporter dye (Molecular Devices) and incubated for approximately 2 hours to allow for dye equilibration. Baseline spontaneous activity will be recorded prior to drug addition. Drugs will then be introduced using the integrated FLIPR liquid handling system. Functional responses will be measured following an additional 2-hour post-exposure period, corresponding to a stabilized network state suitable for analysis. Time-series recordings at 2 Hz will capture spontaneous neuronal activity over a 10-minute recording window, enabling quantification of network dynamics including oscillatory behavior, burst structure, and synchronization. This functional readout is supported by prior studies demonstrating sensitivity of neuronal activity metrics in 3D neural systems [2, 3].

4.2 Feature Representation

Neuronal activity traces will be transformed into quantitative representations using a combination of time-series transformation and chemical fingerprinting approaches. Time-series features will be derived using convolutional kernel-based methods (Hydra), which encode signal morphology and temporal structure [4]. In parallel, functional phenotypes will be characterized relative to reference excitation- and inhibition-dominant states, providing a compact description of network perturbation. Excitation and inhibition states are defined by pharmacological response to 30 μ M 4-aminopyridine and 10 μ M muscimol, respectively. To incorporate chemical information, drugs will be encoded using circular molecular fingerprints generated from canonical SMILES strings following established methods [5]. Functional and chemical features will be combined to produce a unified drug-level representation.

5. Primary and Secondary Endpoints

The primary endpoint is the drug-level classification of seizure liability based on functional activity profiles observed in the cortical organoid assay with performance evaluated against known human clinical outcomes. The objective of this endpoint is to achieve a level of

sensitivity and specificity that meaningfully contributes to the weight of evidence guiding clinical decision making. Predictions will be derived by aggregating replicate- and dose-level measurements into a single drug-level score. Performance will be evaluated using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis and associated metrics, with emphasis on sensitivity at defined specificity thresholds to reflect decision-making contexts in safety assessment.

A secondary endpoint will evaluate the ability of the organoid technology and modeling framework to capture broader neurological adverse event (AE) types beyond seizure liability. Specifically, performance in predicting sedation, neuropsychiatric AEs, neuropathies/DRG, movement disorders, and toxic syndromes (e.g. serotonin syndrome) will be quantified. The same drug-level framework and evaluation metrics will be used.

6. Data Analysis Plan

All data will be analyzed at the drug level using integrated feature representations combining functional activity profiles and SMILES-derived molecular fingerprints. Measurements from individual organoids, doses, and replicates will be retained during feature generation and then averaged to a single drug-level prediction to align with the intended classification task.

Model performance will be evaluated using five-fold cross-validation with drug-level splits ($\approx 80\%$ train / 20% test per fold), ensuring all data for a given drug are confined to a single fold, and generating out-of-fold predictions for every drug. Performance will be quantified using area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC), with additional assessment of operating thresholds using Youden's J statistic to balance sensitivity and specificity. Reported metrics will reflect the average out-of-fold performance across folds, along with variability to assess the stability of the predictive model.

7. Study Outcomes and Interpretation

Results will be evaluated with respect to concordance between assay-derived functional signatures and known clinical seizure outcomes. Particular attention will be given to concentration-dependent effects observed within or near clinically observed exposure ranges. Findings will be interpreted in the context of supporting mechanistic insight into drug-induced perturbations of neuronal network activity.

8. Limitations

As a retrospective non-interventional study, interpretation is subject to limitations including the absence of systemic pharmacokinetic processes, lack of metabolic context, and the inherent constraints of extrapolating *in vitro* exposure to *in vivo* conditions.

9. References

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